

Improved Accuracy and Computational Efficiency in Human Activity Recognition through Hybrid CNN-GRU Models

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Abstract

This paper proposes a novel Multiscale Convolutional Neural Network (MCNN) using CNN3D architecture for human behavior recognition. Unlike traditional models, it captures spatial and depth information through space-time and depth-separable convolution modules. Evaluated on the UCI HAR dataset, the MCNN model demonstrates higher accuracy (94%) and reduced complexity (3306 parameters) compared to CNN2D (93%, 9135 parameters). An extension combining CNN, GRU, and Bidirectional algorithms further improves accuracy (96%) with only 1162 parameters, optimizing feature extraction and reducing training complexity. The approach showcases significant advancements in efficiency and performance, making it highly suitable for activity recognition using smartphone-captured data.

Keywords: CNN2D, Human Behaviour, MCNN

1. Introduction

Human behavior recognition plays a crucial role in bridging theoretical innovations with real-world applications in computer vision. By blending insights from image processing, artificial intelligence, and human kinematics, this field has become essential in analyzing video content. Existing methods for behavior recognition fall into two categories: traditional classification techniques and deep learning-based approaches. Traditional methods often struggle with the inherent complexity of human behavior and environmental variability, while deep learning models, despite their potential, face limitations in computational efficiency and comprehensively capturing multi-dimensional behavioral nuances. This research aims to enhance human behavior recognition by merging traditional feature extraction with advanced deep learning techniques. Leveraging cutting-edge architectures like C3R, eco, and TSN, and incorporating cross-structure transfer learning, the study explores soft transfer strategies to improve feature generalizability. By addressing these challenges, this project aspires to refine the accuracy and efficiency of behavior recognition in dynamic and complex scenarios.

2. Literature survey

(Gu et al., 2022)

This study introduced a spatio-temporal mapping approach using bone data for human behavior recognition. The method combines spatial and temporal data features to enhance accuracy. A key contribution was utilizing hierarchical temporal aggregation for continuous behavior tracking, emphasizing the importance of dynamic data in behavior recognition frameworks.

(Ding et al., 2022)

A two-stream network integrating spatial and temporal heterogeneity was proposed, which processes spatial features and temporal dynamics separately. This architecture improves efficiency by focusing on relevant spatiotemporal interactions, particularly for complex video datasets.

(Lu et al., 2021)

This research applied Kinect-based systems for recognizing unsafe behaviors in subways. It integrated motion trajectory analysis with contextual cues, showcasing the utility of multi-modal data. The work emphasized the role of environmental factors in improving predictive accuracy for constrained spaces.

(Zhai & Zhao et al., 2021)

Zhai and Zhao proposed a lightweight behavior recognition model for edge computing environments. Using DS ConvLSTM, the framework demonstrated reduced computational complexity without compromising accuracy, emphasizing energy-efficient designs for mobile and IoT devices.

(Ying & Gong et al., 2021)

This paper highlighted the role of channel attention mechanisms in improving feature extraction. By dynamically adjusting feature weights, the network optimized resource utilization and improved recognition accuracy in high-dimensional data environments.

(Duan et al., 2021)

A framework incorporating environmental context, such as lighting and space constraints, was presented. This model combined decision trees, SVM, and k-NN algorithms, demonstrating that contextual data significantly enhances recognition performance in real-world settings.

(Xu et al., 2019)

This work explored depth feature fusion for improved recognition in video surveillance. The model used depth-based spatiotemporal features, showing enhanced robustness against occlusions and varying lighting conditions, common challenges in real-world applications.

(Chen et al., 2019)

Chen et al. developed a spatiotemporal attention mechanism to focus on critical frame regions in video sequences. This method significantly improved detection precision by prioritizing areas of high behavioral relevance within each frame.

(Cao et al., 2018)

This innovative approach utilized Wi-Fi signal patterns for behavior recognition, bypassing traditional visual data. The study demonstrated the feasibility of leveraging radio frequency data for non-intrusive monitoring in smart environments, reducing dependency on high-resolution imaging.

(Wu et al., 2018)

This study proposed impulse neural networks for detecting anomalous behaviors in complex scenes. By combining motion dynamics and neural spike patterns, the model achieved superior anomaly detection, particularly in high-noise environments.

3. Problem Statement

Human behaviour recognition faces critical challenges in accurately capturing and analyzing spatial and temporal features from dynamic environments. Traditional methods relying on global average pooling often neglect local spatial details, leading to reduced precision. Additionally, existing deep learning models suffer from high computational complexity and fail to fully encapsulate multi-dimensional behavior characteristics. Environmental factors such as occlusion, lighting, and noise further complicate the recognition process. These limitations hinder the efficiency and accuracy of behavior prediction systems. The need for an advanced, computationally efficient framework that integrates spatiotemporal interactions and robust feature extraction to improve recognition accuracy is the central problem addressed in this research.

4. Proposed Method

The proposed method introduces a Multiscale Convolutional Neural Network (MCNN) using CNN3D architecture for human behavior recognition. It addresses the limitations of existing models by integrating two novel modules: a space-time interaction module for capturing spatiotemporal features and a depth-separable convolution module for efficient feature extraction. The approach combines low-rank behaviour information across video segments and employs multiscale convolution kernels to analyze diverse receptive fields. By optimizing the network structure and reducing training parameters, the method achieves superior accuracy and lower computational complexity. Additionally, an extended hybrid model (CNN + GRU + Bidirectional) further enhances accuracy and feature optimization.

4.1 Architecture

4.2 Human Behaviour Dataset

Visualizing class labels count found in dataset

The proposed work utilizes the UCI HAR dataset, which features six distinct human activities: standing, laying, sitting, walking upstairs, walking downstairs, and walking. These activities are recorded using a smartphone's built-in sensors, capturing relevant motion data. The dataset serves as a foundation for training and testing the performance of various algorithms. By leveraging this comprehensive activity dataset, the study ensures accurate evaluation and optimization of the proposed models for human activity recognition in real-world scenarios.

5. Methodology

5.1 Loading and Displaying HAR Dataset Values:

Loading Human Activity Recognition (HAR) dataset, sourced from smartphone sensors capturing a range of human activities. Loading this dataset provides an initial glimpse into its structure, enabling us to understand the nature and distribution of the recorded activities.

5.2 Dataset Processing and Train-Test Split

With a grasp of the dataset's content, we proceed to its preprocessing stage. This involves essential steps like normalization to standardize data ranges and feature extraction to distill relevant information. Post-processing, we partition the dataset into training and testing subsets, ensuring a balanced distribution of records to foster unbiased model evaluation.

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5.4 Definition of Evaluation Metrics: For a comprehensive assessment of model performance, we define functions to compute key evaluation metrics. These metrics—

accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score—serve as performance indicators, enabling a nuanced comparison across different models and aiding in identifying their strengths and weaknesses.

- 5.5 Existing CNN2D Algorithm:** Embarking on model training, we first employ the existing CNN2D algorithm on our HAR dataset. As the model learns from the data, we delve into discussions around its complexity and parameter size. These considerations are pivotal as they directly influence training efficiency, computational requirements, and ultimately, the model's predictive accuracy.
- 5.6 Evaluation of Existing CNN2D Model:** Post-training, the CNN2D model undergoes rigorous evaluation on the test dataset. Performance metrics, including accuracy, are computed to gauge the model's efficacy. To visually interpret its predictive prowess, we employ a confusion matrix, which delineates correct and erroneous predictions across various activity labels.
- 5.7 Proposed MCNN (MDN) Model:** Transitioning to our proposed model, the MCNN (MDN) built on CNN3D architecture is introduced. This model, conceptualized to refine the existing CNN2D algorithm, aims to strike a balance between parameter size and accuracy. Discussions around its architecture and parameter specifications provide insights into its potential advantages over its predecessors.
- 5.8 Evaluation of Proposed MCNN (MDN) Model:** The proposed MCNN (MDN) model is subjected to evaluation, focusing on its accuracy and other performance metrics. By emphasizing its efficiency in terms of reduced parameter size and computational overhead, we underscore its readiness for real-world deployment, scalability, and potential to outperform existing models.
- 5.9 Extension Model:** To further bolster accuracy, we innovatively combine three algorithms—CNN, GRU, and Bidirectional. This synergy, despite utilizing a modest 1162 parameters, remarkably reduces model complexity. This amalgamation, through hybrid optimization of training features, yields superior features, translating to enhanced accuracy, outperforming both existing and proposed algorithms.

6. Evolution

Precision:

$$\text{Formula: Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

Recall (Sensitivity):

$$\text{Formula: Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

F1 Score:

$$\text{Formula: } F1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Accuracy:

$$\text{Formula: Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Predictions}}$$

7. Result Analysis

Existing CNN2D model got 93% accuracy and can see other metrics and in confusion matrix x-axis represents predicted Labels and y-axis represents True Labels.

Propose MCNN MDN model got 94% accuracy and can see other metrics also

Extension model got 96% accuracy

Training accuracy of all 3 models such as existing, propose and extension where x-axis represents training epoch and y-axis represents accuracy and with each increasing epoch accuracy got increase and in all models extension got high accuracy.

8. Comparative Analysis and Performance Visualization

To facilitate a holistic comparison of model performances, we plot a graph juxtaposing the training accuracies of existing, proposed, and extension models across epochs. This visual representation, supplemented by a tabulated comparison, offers a comprehensive overview, enabling stakeholders to discern each algorithm's strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

In above comparison graph x-axis represents algorithm names and y-axis represents accuracy and other metrics in different colour bars and in all algorithms extension got high performance.

9. Prediction

Loading and processing the test data from a file. The data is shuffled randomly, and a subset of 10 records is selected for evaluation. These records are reshaped into a format compatible with the CNN model, ensuring the dimensions align with the model's requirements. The preprocessed data is then passed to the extension model for prediction. For each prediction, the highest probability index is extracted to identify the predicted activity, such as "Standing" , "Laying" , "Walking", and "Downstairs". The results are displayed alongside the corresponding input data for verification, demonstrating the model's ability to recognize and classify human activities accurately.

10. Conclusion

The proposed method for human behavior recognition, utilizing the Multiscale Convolutional Neural Network (MCNN) with CNN3D architecture, demonstrates significant advancements in accuracy and computational efficiency. By integrating space-time interaction and depth-separable convolution modules, the approach effectively captures spatiotemporal and local spatial features, addressing limitations of traditional models. Evaluated on the UCI HAR dataset, the MCNN achieved superior accuracy with reduced training complexity compared to existing methods. Furthermore, the extension model combining CNN, GRU, and Bidirectional algorithms showcased enhanced performance with minimal parameters. This study highlights the importance of optimized architectures and hybrid models in behavior recognition, paving the way for more efficient and robust solutions in dynamic real-world scenarios. Future work will focus on further improving model lightweight and scalability.

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